

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM WITH THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE GALAPAGOS ISLANDS-ECUADOR

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ABSTRACT

At present, sustainable tourism has become an important activity in the economic development of a country, in order to maintain an environmental balance and to conserve natural and cultural resources. Implementing sustainable tourism in a country will depend on its potential. Tourism worldwide has been boosted by the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), with the use of business models that focus on Internet Marketing. In order to analyze the implications that ICTs have on tourism in Ecuador, this investigation was carried out. This study

is focused on determining how sustainable tourism in the Galapagos Islands can strengthen this sector in the country using ICT as a tool. The methodology to carry out this research was through an extensive bibliographic review that involved a number of scientific, institutional and governmental articles. This search managed to make a clear definition of sustainable tourism, information related to the demand for tourism in the Galapagos archipelago was collected and, in this way, implement a management guided by sustainability and be able to offer a service that allows the destination to be more attractive. Finally, in the study of this practical case, different factors were taken into account that helped the application of sustainable development and that were analyzed with all the possible proposals, in addition to being able to give a detailed explanation of what tourism is like in the Galapagos Islands. It is important to mention that the sources consulted showed that sustainable tourism allows intertwining the economic, social and environmental aspects that are needed to strengthen tourism in Ecuador. Sustainable tourism has become a methodology of great importance at the economic level in the country, generating new sources of employment and providing the necessary support for work and paving the way for a better social, economic and political coexistence in the world, presenting a series of particularities that are studied from the observations obtained from the experience lived in Ecuador which serve as a basis to produce a renewal in the activities that are traditional and that are lasting over time. Keywords: sustainable tourism, Galapagos Islands, sustainability, TIC.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently the tourism sector represents worldwide one of the main mechanisms that drive the economy of the countries, there are increasingly demanding customers so it has experienced constant changes that involve including innovative ideas and strategies (Moreno, 2011). The fact that demand in this sector has increased in various areas and in the same way the supply, has revealed a series of imbalances that have caused problems at social level and the environment. By virtue of this, the implementation of a tourism model that is sustainable begins to be necessary. (Araña Padilla & León González, 2017)

The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2015) mentions that tourism is consolidated as an activity that has acquired more importance in the economic field around the world, whose projections indicate that the entry of international tourists per year may increase by 3.3% in the period from 2010 to 2030 worldwide. According to this premise, it is necessary that the countries involved have to be focused on motivating the promotion of tourism with greater exclusivity, competition and diversity. It is important to mention that tourism worldwide had a growth of 4% in 2019 compared to 2018. However, a decrease in tourism activity was reported in the first quarter of 2020 as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic (World Tourism Organization, 2020).

Nowadays every project that is carried out in any sector of the economy from its planning includes everything related to sustainability or sustainable development, with the aim of providing greater value to it from its approach to its procedure, considering that sustainability represents one of the fundamental pillars for the development of the planning process. However, over time the tourism

sector has not been considered as a key sector during the design of the processes that constitute planning, even though it is a sector that has acquired great relevance for the economy of a large number of countries in the world (Bertoni, 2008).

The concept of sustainability has become important since daily there is a greater pressure of the human being on the care that must be taken to the environment, and to carry out compliance with the principles of conservation, the reduction of the different negative impacts and the ecological footprint generated by economic activities in order to guarantee a better future (University of San Francisco, 2014). In the United Nations Brundtland Report, the definition of sustainable development is as follows "*meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs*" (Bermejo, 2014, p. 15). , due to this lately within the world economies and productive systems has focused on the promotion of respect and preservation of the environment, so that they can guarantee the existence of sufficient resources to meet the needs of future generations affirmed in a technological system that is friendly to the environment (Castro and Marrugo, 2018). The above is in line with the indications made by Castro & Anturi (2015) that mention that the administration of resources must be carried out in a responsible manner so that people in the future have themselves. The tourism sector does not escape this reality, it is necessary that they must function harmoniously with the environment and in correspondence with the current legal requirements established worldwide.

The activities of the tourism sector have experienced a considerable increase in recent years, so it is necessary to establish an environmental legal framework to which companies belonging to this sector can proactively adapt. At the local level, a tourism development model capable of generating significant environmental, social and economic impacts has been applied. That is why this work aims to study the basic concepts related to sustainable tourism, in addition to analyzing the application of it in the Galapagos Islands.

In 2008 in Ecuador, the new Constitution was approved and the modification in the country's development tactics was carried out, giving an opening to a novel socio-political context in the country by designing new ways to relate the environment, society and the economy (Loor et al., 2018). Research carried out by the "*Global Wellness Institute*" records tourism considered wellness as one of the activities capable of generating the highest income worldwide.

In this context, it seeks to collect information related to the demand for tourism in the Galapagos archipelago and thus implement a management guided by sustainability and be able to offer a service that allows the destination to become more attractive. At the natural level, anthropogenic damage has generated great impacts that unfortunately have increased every day, which is why it is necessary to make great efforts for conservation aimed at protecting the diversity that exists on the islands, in addition to providing ecological solutions. (Belly, 2015)

Once all the information has been collected, a concept of what sustainable tourism means will be generated, and then proceed to its application to the practical case of Ecuador and its islands. In the execution of this practical case, different factors that contribute to the application of sustainable development will be taken into account and all possible proposals will be analyzed, in addition

to giving a detailed explanation such as tourism in the Galapagos Islands, through the consultation of research previous and the different trends that arise in the tourism field in the world.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This research will have as an object of study sustainable tourism, so it will be related to tourism carried out in the Galapagos Islands. It is very important to mention the relevance of tourism in Ecuador as a sector of great hierarchy at a strategic level, since it presents the capacity to generate qualified employment in the country.

Tourism worldwide

Among the main contributors of the economy in the world is the tourism sector, which has evolved based on the demands of customers who are increasing, causing this sector to experiment in each of its spaces a series of innovations that allow a more satisfactory attention to the needs manifested by customers (Araña Padilla & León González, 2017).

Based on data provided by certified entities, in 2018 tourism was responsible for generating around 7% of trade in the world, with the consequent generation of new jobs, estimating that one person for every ten people obtained employment in the world, providing the means they require for the livelihoods of millions of people in many developed and developing countries. (Buades, 2019)

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused a significant negative impact worldwide for both social and economic development. However, measures such as the suspension of international travel led to the establishment of geographical barriers that no longer existed between countries, generating a globalisation in the world (Niewiadomski, 2020).

Effects of the pandemic on the tourism sector:

In this century there have been very radical changes that have affected the ecosystems on the planet. Global history has shown that pandemics have had serious political, social and economic consequences. The existence of various pandemics in this century has negatively affected the world economy, resulting in a large number of human losses in addition to economic ones. Currently, several investigations have been carried out with the aim of knowing the effects generated on certain tourist destinations by the COVID-19 pandemic, in which it is concluded that most of the tourist destinations in the world were altered by the pandemic. (Torres & Fernández, 2020)

With the presence of past pandemics, activity in the tourism sector suffered effects at the local level, unlike the consequences produced by the COVID-19 pandemic, which have generated profound transformations in tourism, thus affecting supply and demand in the same way. (Folinas & Metaxas, 2020)

From the perspective of supply, the emergence of COVID-19 has introduced many changes in all sectors to be able to adapt to the new reality, among which is the activation of different sanitary

protocols that involves the disinfection of hands with hydroalcoholic gels or with alcohol, limit the number of people and their Permanence in spaces or establishments, lthe implementation of distancing between people, and the establishment of different schedules at mealtimes, although at present there are places where limitations in tourism have decreased, only It recommends respect for the protocols established for biosecurity, such as the use of the mask and maintaining distance between people, especially in places that are public.(Hoque, Hasanat, Arif, & Hamid, 2020)

On the other hand, at present we must also face otherchanges that human activities require, such as accelerated digitalization and the introduction of robotics and artificial intelligence in hotels in order to increasehealth safety in theseestablishments. which is considered to be a point of greatimportance for the recovery experienced by the tourism sector during the post-COVID ET. To respond to the growing demand, most tourist destinations will be obliged to carry out the incorporation and digital transformation, which involve all those technologies that do not require contact (touchless technologies) until Thedifferent processesare necessary for the automation of services.(Niewiadomski, 2020)

The tourist destinations with the highest demand at present must face di versproblems, such as the saturation of the territories, which usually exceed the load capacity, so it is necessary to implement measures that are adequate and that prevent the agglomeration of tourists in the different zones and at certain times. Another problemis the creationof new tourist destinations which have progressively increased their demand becoming a serious competition both nationally and internationally (Torres & Fernández, 2020).

In relation to demand in the sector, the COVID-19 pandemic has generated a significant change in the behavior of users, which is influenced by the interaction between different internal and external factors such as motivation. , attitudes, beliefs, environment, security, socio-cultural and economic aspects . (Dinarto, Wanto, & Sebastian, 2020)

Environmental sustainability

Theincrease in both demand and supply of tourism in certain areas has led to a number of imbalances which have caused a large number of social and environmental problems. The creation of a tourism model with principles of sustainability became necessary, however, it is only at the Congress of the International Association of Scientific Experts on Tourism in 1991 that it is defined, pointing out at this meeting that the Sustainable tourism is the type of tourism where the ecological, social and economic interests of the different areas where it is developed are balanced.(Acerenza, 2006)

It is in the twentieth century that sustainable development is brought into account in all the various activities of the world, but it is at the beginning of the year 2000 that It awakens a greater awareness of the impact on the environment due to human activity in addition to the pressure exerted by various interest groups with the intention of developing different measures to reduce the damage caused by these activities(Acerenza, 2006).

Sustainability represents one of the mechanisms that is considered fundamental in any planning procedure. However, some authors consider that the tourism sector is generally not seen as oneor more of the key priority issues in the common procedures that correspond to the procedureor

planning, even if it has an important impact on the at the economic level in various regions (Connell, 2009)

Sustainability aims to protect natural resources and the improper occupation of sites with the intention of reducing environmental pollution and trying to make the activity economically durable over time and that the social and cultural characteristics of the receiving areas (Bertoni, 2008) can be preserved. Sustainable development set out in Brundtland's report is development capable of meeting current needs without risk the ability to meet the needs of generations in the future (Santos-Quintero, 2004).

Sustainable tourism:

The tourism company is considered to be one of the largest and largest industries. This is found all over the world, so the environmental, social and economic impacts are also evaluated worldwide. The different impacts that are generated by this industry can be both positive and negative, depending on the way they are perceived, that is, if they affect or favor. Tourism is considered sustainable when it is sought to have a minimum negative impact, which translates into the maximization of the economic benefit and therefore leading to the minimum or the damages that can be caused to the environment. (Araña Padilla & León González, 2017)

On the other hand, ecotourism is known as a type of tourism considered as sustainable, it is usually executed in areas that are natural that are not usually explored, considered as sensitive at an environmental and social level, especially when indigenous groups that inhabit the area are involved, being able to have a net impact that can be positive or negative. (Good, 2006)

Ecotourism seeks to highlight positive impacts through an approach based on conserving, educating travellers and generating benefits for hosts. However, there are few companies capable of achieving these objectives, some lie about the achievements generated while there are others who do not care. (Buades, 2019)

In general, sustainable activities are referred to as those that carry out a certain action that is executed in an identical or similar way in an indefinite time, and in addition it is sustainable over time when it complies with three elements such as They are: the economic, defined when the processes that are carried out, start and end with some rapidity by practices at the enterprise level that are not adequate, nevertheless make an economic contribution to the locality. Enterprises that are usually regarded as sustainable have the characteristic that they benefit their owners, neighbours and workers alike.

With respect to the environmental part, it is referred to all that damage that may be caused to the flora, fauna, water and soil, among others, which must be minimized by the company, looking for ways to achieve the conservation of the environment through the elaboration of programs designed to conserve and protect itself. With regard to the social and cultural aspects, generally in these areas there is no damage on the part of the company, on the contrary, it tries to produce changes that are favorable or that allow the revitalization of both structures seen in the community where the activity takes place. (Galera Navarro & Torres Rogan, 2019)

By bearing in mind the above aspects, it is said that profitability is achieved, or in other words good is being done. This means that the organization carries out its activities in a way that does

not produce an adverse effect or in the environmental, economic or cultural fields. When companies are managed in this way, they can carry out their activities with the generation of profits and in turn generate benefits to the environment and nearby communities (Galera Navarro & Torres Rogan, 2019).

It is important to emphasize that the foundations that constitute sustainability can be applied regardless of the type of tourism such as city or jungle, beach, low or large scale or specialized. They can be used in the same way in different sectors that constitute this industry such as: expeditions, land operators, accommodation, agencies and transport. In the Agenda 21 for the Tourism and Travel Industry they refer to the fact that the products obtained from sustainable tourism are usually functional products and that they do so in harmony with the environment, as well as with the community and with the cultures of the localities. receiving these permanent benefits (Araña Padilla & León González, 2017).

Benefits of sustainable tourism

Sustainable tourism has as its main objective to generate a minimum impact or take it to zero in the locality where it is developed. Ecotourism is considered a type of sustainable tourism, it is usually practiced in natural areas that have not been explored, that socially and environmentally are sensitive, especially when an indigenous group that lives in the area is involved, can generate a positive impact or advers. (By Lourdes Canul & Santander, 2014)

Based on the above, this type of tourism seeks to highlight the positive impacts through the implementation of an approach based on conservation, educating all visitors and generating important benefits for the who participate as hosts, being a minority of companies capable of achieving these purposes, there are others who lie about the achievements they achieve and there are also others who do not care. (Buades, 2019)

The benefits that are produced by sustainable tourism at the environmental level are: to give a correct use to environmental resources and in this way to maintain all ecological processes, the protection of biodiversity and contribute to the maintenance of natural resources by causing a minimum impact to the environment. Another benefit is in the social field, trying to integrate all the communities that are located around where the tourist activity takes place; On the other hand, carrying out this type of tourism also brings as a benefit the generation of direct jobs for the inhabitants of the Community. The implementation of this type of tourism encourages the development of companies such as travel agencies, transport, accommodation, recreational and others aimed at glimpsing what the sector requires, representing this other benefits of sustainable tourism. At the economic level, great benefits are also generated by the introduction of foreign currency into the country, increasing the economic capital of the sector where it is carried out. Tourism considered sustainable has as one of its main characteristics to respect and maintain the sociocultural legitimacy of the communities active within the locality, preserving and enhancing all its assets and all its traditional values. (Acerenza, 2006)

Impact of ICTs on sustainable tourism

At present, ICT has evolved vertiginously which has caused the tourism business sector to have to be updated on a daily basis, generating aspects such as extra money to modernize technology, professional training in the use of ICT, redistribution of spaces among others. At the same time, it has also had to face changes directly related to trade, competition and other economic sectors, which also involve tourism, generating that companies have to reinvent and innovate in order to take over the market using various ways that includes of course the internet.

At this time there is a large number of online pages that are responsible for offering services such as: flights, hotels, restaurants, cultural activities among others, to a certain location. There are also other pages despite not being companies dedicated to the tourism sector are responsible for providing tourist information on places of interest, promotions, among others. In addition to this there are pages designed exclusively to comment on the services offered by different companies where users can place their opinion, criticism or point of view of the services and attentions received, making evident their approval or not of the experience lived, which will serve as a guide for future tourists.

The above mentioned could give two readings, on the one hand, tourism companies will try to strive to improve the quality of service to customers so that it can meet their expectations, while on the other hand there are customers with expectations are very high even when the selected service fits the available budget, which means that generally customers want five-star services paying only for one of three. Something that is counterproductive for companies since their prestige and stability are at stake, at the moment that the client gives his appreciation of the service received. Finally, it can be mentioned that companies must take into account both the advantages and disadvantages that ICT can offer them.

3. METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS

This article is framed in a bibliographic review and for its development we proceeded to carry out an exhaustive search of documents related to the subject both scientific and institutional and governmental, extracted from different search engines, *Scielo, Dialnet, Redalyc and Google Scholar*, using keywords, "sustainable tourism / sustainable tourism; Galapagos Islands/Galapagos Islands; sustainability. For the present research, articles no older than 10 years were selected. However, due to the contribution of relevant information for the development of the topic, some studies were included even when they exceeded the established range.

4. SUSTAINABLE TOURISM IN ECUADOR

The development of tourism in Ecuador as a state policy, is exposed on April 19, 2001 when Executive Decree 1424 was published in Official Gazette 309, establishing objectives that must be met according to Article 4 of the tourism law, where tourism activity must be identified as an initiative whereas it can be Community and private, the State being responsible for enhancing all activities carried out by promoting tourism which is competitive; ensuring that all the country's resources are used rationally; it must coordinate with other governmental bodies at national and regional level in order to achieve the objectives set; in order to achieve the objectives,

it is necessary to motivate staff to obtain adequate professional and technical training; There must be promotion of the country and its attractions internationally through the help of other entities, whether public or private. (Belly, 2015)

Galapagos Islands:

• History:

In the twentieth century begins to populate the archipelago of the Galapagos, because these islands were uninhabited being manifested by Fray Tomas de Berlanga in the year 1535. (Belly, 2015) In 1973 the Galapagos archipelago received the designation of province of Ecuador, and this was accessed by three cantons that were called islands which are: Santa Cruz, San Cristobal, and Isabela. On February 12, 1832, it was when the idente pres Juan José Flores, joined him to Ecuador. By 1978, the group of islands were declared a World Heritage Site and their economy depends mainly on the income from tourism to be visited by around 200,000 tourists annually. (Maggí, Rodríguez, Litardo, & Caviedes, 2018)

Galapagos is currently the only protected site in Ecuador, following a Special Law which was passed in 1998. This law was the product of a participatory procedure involving various authors who were essential in the different sectors operating in the archipelago. This group of islands were declared a national park in addition to being an important biosphere reserve and that in its surroundings it has a high content of endemic species that are achieved both in the fauna and in the flora, constituting one of the main tourist attractions that has acquired great importance for the country. (Ruiz-Ballesteros, 2017)

• Geography:

The group of islands constitute an archipelago that belongs to the Pacific Ocean and is located on the coasts of Ecuador at 972 km. The archipelago is made up of 13 large islands with an area of approximately 10^{km²} and 215 smaller islands located around the land line of the equator. Among the largest islands are: Santa Cruz, Isabela, Fernandina, Santiago, Floreana, San Cristobal and Marchena. Among the smaller islands are: Genovesa, Pinta, Española and Baltra. (Grenier, 2007) There are around 30,000 inhabitants on the islands, with Santa Cruz having the largest number of inhabitants, followed by the island of Isabela, Floreana and San Cristóbal. It was at the beginning of the 1900s when the archipelago began to be populated, arriving at this time the first inhabitants and carrying out its colonization, however, the largest increase in population was recorded in recent decades and is attributed to the vertiginous boom in tourism. (Watkins & Cruz, 2007)

• Flora and fauna:

These islands are also known as The Enchanted Islands, and this name was assigned in the sixteenth century due to its impressive biodiversity in both flora and fauna, being known for the large number of species that are endemic, so there are carried out on a series of studies by the

scientist Charles Darwin that allowed him to confirm his discoveries about the theory of evolution due to natural selection. (Grenier, 2007)

Regarding the fauna that exists in the Galapagos archipelago, it can be divided into: native and endemic. Among the most common species are: sea turtles, iguanas, lizards, albatrosses, penguins, cormorants and sea lions. On the other hand, these Galapagos Islands have the characteristic of being one of the most active sites with respect to volcanoes, so they are called hot spots or "hot spots". This archipelago is known as the second of the archipelagos that has the most volcanic activity on the planet surpassing Hawaii. The flora has a great variety in the Galapagos Islands which is estimated to be due to the high amount of habitats as to in the islands as in their surroundings, this has forced the different species to adapt to environmental conditions that are specific in each island and that present continuous changes in the ecosystems of an island when the procedure or succession occurs. (Lanteri, 2001)

This archipelago has one of the largest marine reserves in the world, with approximately 138,000 km² receiving the same importance as those that exist in the Great Coral Bar of Australia. These islands of the archipelago are home to approximately 2,909 species, among which approximately 18.2% are endemic, and due to being unique acquired great biological importance, this archipelago being one of the most popular destinations worldwide. (Apples, 2007)

One of the largest reserves of the National System of Protected Areas of Ecuador is the Galapagos National Park. About 97% of the total land area corresponding to the archipelago is constituted by the Galapagos National Park reserve. As it was cited in previous paragraphs, this archipelago was declared by UNESCO as a Natural Heritage of Humanity in 1979. (Watkins & Cruz, 2007)

• Galapagos Islands Tourism

It is estimated that it was 15 years ago when the growth of tourism in the Galapagos Islands began, being reported an annual growth close to 14%, on the other hand, there was also an increase in the population and with it the increase in the risk of pollution and the arrival of species considered invasive. Among the causes of the rapid growth of the population are the high rates of migration of all people coming from other parts of the continent to the islands, who move in search of better conditions to survive. employment and better opportunities for their families. In this sense, the number of people who enter the islands either as tourists or as migrants is closely associated with problems such as the entry of disturbing species of flora and fauna that are The increase in pollution in the environment, and the pressure due to the limited natural resources existing in the archipelago. (Ruiz-Ballesteros, 2017)

At the same time that there are these serious risks that affect the economy of the archipelago, the tourist boom in the Galapagos Islands has achieved countless benefits for its health, and has contributed to the push to carry out other businesses related to tourism in the locality. (Grenier, 2007)

Other research indicates that at the beginning of the 60s and 70s was that tourism began in these Islands, observing in the 80s an accelerated growth of tourist activities in them with a large number of visitors of around 200,000 per year. The tourism that began in the Galapagos Islands was through the modality of small sailboats or boats used by fishermen who came to visit existing

for the time as one of the main attractions the exuberant nature of the archipelago, so it was considered. By many of the authors the beginning of sustainable tourism in these islands. (Watkins & Cruz, 2007)

Due to the vertiginous increase in the number of tourists, and due to the need to provide a better service, it was possible to move to the use of cruise ships which offered better comforts and had a greater capacity for accommodation. Starting to work with the category of local tourism, in response to a participation that was more active in this type of business. In this new modality which is characterized because the tourist has more contact with the inhabitants of the locality and who are responsible for the reception of large numbers is tourists. With this modality, many of the residents conditioned their homes with the purpose of receiving visitors who arrive on the islands that have been populated, even though there are many homes that do not offer the minimum quality standards. (Belly, 2015)

Currently, as a business, tourism has achieved around \$ 418 million annually as an estimated value, where approximately \$ 60 million are converted into a reserve for the economy of the islands constituting the main source of income of all Galapagos. At present, Galapagos has undergone a series of transformations and has become one of the destinations for tourism that presents a significant relevance worldwide, being the responsibility of all the inhabitants and entities of the islands to minimize to the maximum the adverse impact derived from activities carried out in the environment.

- **Tourism economy in the Galapagos Islands**

In the country the gross income each year experiences an increase of approximately 14% which comes from tourism as the main mechanism contributing to the economic, cultural and social change of the country. The percentage of income is usually higher in the Galapagos Islands area an important part of its economy in addition to being favored by the investments made by the national government, private donations and multi and bilateral supports. (Mullo Romero, Vera Peña, & Guillén Herrera, 2019)

The fishing sector contributes approximately 4% of the total income in the Galapagos Islands, highlighting sea cucumber fishing as one of the most important activities during the nineties. It should be noted that one of the most important aspects turned out to be economic incentives and subsidies, since these favoured the accelerated growth of tourism. (Watkins & Cruz, 2007)

The tourist activity at the economic level has been of great relevance and is reflected in the achievements obtained and those that have been enjoyed during the last years, since it represents the activity that at the economic level has greater power in the future. (Santos-Quintero, 2004)

Tourism constitutes an important part of the economy of the country is, so it is necessary the existence of a relationship between the different constituent companies, such as inns, tour operators, carriers, beverage and food companies To set objectives which will guide scientific and technological progress in this sector, which will be reflected in the quality of service, safety and comfort and the speed with which the Services offered to tourists. (Picornell, 2015)

- **Types of tourism offered by the Galapagos Islands**

The archipelago offers several options to travel and know the Galapagos Islands, an option is considered ideal for tourists who have a small budget and consists of doing it independently, through the search by the Visitor to tourism agencies that offer tours that are more economically accessible. A second option is a little more expensive, which is to take a cruise, for this the tourist must move to Puerto Ayora from Baltra Island, and can be done from three to more days.

It is necessary to emphasize that tourists must have cash, this because in the archipelago there are very few ATMs. It is also necessary to keep in mind, to know what are the requirements that are requested by the authorities in the places where the archipelago is accessed, such as at the airport. These Islands have a high demand in the high season so the offer in hotels is wide and available for different budgets, there are going from pensions to hotels and hostels whose prices vary depending on comfort and the area where they are located.

It is important to note that at present there are several companies dedicated to tourism, among which is Cruising Galapagos SA, which has as its main objective to maintain economic and social practices adapted according to the weakness of the archipelago. In the economy of a country, tourism is one of the very important elements being necessary the existence of a relationship of dependence between the organizations that constitute it, among which are the inns, tour operators, retailers, recreational companies and transport companies, food companies, beverages, among others. The introduction of technology is a factor that determines the progress of this sector which is manifested in greater safety, speed, quality of service and comfort offered to visitors (Viloria, 2012).

Currently in the Galapagos Islands two types of tourism are carried out: the first consists of navigable tours that are carried out on boats and the second type is locally based. During the development of this study it has been evidenced that both types of tourism have certain controversies to a level environmental, because they make use of the natural spaces of the Galapagos Islands to carry out all the activities. It is really shocking that both types of tourism have experienced a vertiginous boom and the number of annual travelers is around 300,000 tourists, which is considered very favorable since the limit of visitors before registered for the year 2005 stands at 100,000 tourists. Tourism in the Galapagos Islands is experiencing an early overcrowding due to the presence of low-cost tourism, considered backpackers practiced by visitors who do not care about conservation or protecting the environment and who do not provide resources. Important monetary resources in the islands. (Mullo Romero, Vera Peña, & Guillén Herrera, 2019)

The companies offer various promotions with the route of a destination with sun and beach, leads to the agencies that provide the service to the travelers to carry out a modification in the profile of the tourists, changing to a more specialized tourist, with greater ecological knowledge, motivated by the protection and the conservation of nature and that benefits in a balanced way from the services on earth taking into account the different environmental impacts that it brings. However, the type of tourism that is most common on the islands is locally-based tourism. On the other hand, tourism carried out in large ships is carried out with special attention to the damage

caused to the environment, social and economic damage , prevailing the need to establish the benefits generated by such activity and the services it promotes.

In recent years, tourism in the Galapagos Islands has been increasing, in the last census carried out in 2015 it was recorded that the archipelago has a population of 25,124 inhabitants, making it one of the provinces that has experienced greater growth. For the present inhabitants, there is an overpopulation which is increased thanks to the migration of people illegally to the islands, who are filling the existing job vacancies and which should be filled by the locals, the high migration in addition to the Uncontrolled tourism has generated a series of consequences such as the introduction to the island of exotic species generating adverse impact on the environment and endangering the ecosystems of the archipelago.(Saeteros, Da Silva, & Calles, 2017)

Due to the above, the Ecuadorian Government considers as a mission the implementation of sustainable tourism, establishing it as a prototype or more viable development for tourism practices throughout the Galapagos region, considering as its primary objective to achieve a sustainable management of all. natural resources that allow it to supply the maximum environmental, economic, aesthetic and social needs, respecting and maintaining cultural integrity at and through the inclusion of all social actors in management procedures. It is a priority in the Galapagos Islands to generate the necessary resources that allow them to liquidate some debt that have been accumulated.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of sustainable tourism provides a series of material and cultural benefits and tries to educate the population by raising awareness about the importance of protecting the environment and its value at an economic level, in addition to developing the sense of belonging through the diversification that has been achieved. based on the sources generating income.

At present in Ecuador, sustainable tourism has become a methodology of great importance at the economic level in the country, generating new sources of employment and providing the necessary support for work and opening the way to a better social, economic and political coexistence in the world, resenting a series of particularities that They are studied from the observations obtained from the experience lived in Ecuador which serve as a basis to produce a renewal in the activities que son traditional and that are lasting over time.

This work served as a guide to be able to carry out the resizing on the concepts and elements that constitute sustainable tourism and in addition to assessing its importance at a social, economic and political level; and in this way to be able to establish the responsibilities corresponding to the academic staff and research given the uncertainty that this type of tourism is valued by individuals, whether local or visitors, who can establish certain comparisons with sun and beach tourism.

Finally, it can be concluded that the Galapagos Islands are considered an excellent tourist destination, being an element that motivates the visit, and in turn the urban area that is complemented by the beautiful natural environment, and that is influenced by the various existing

attractions for both domestic and foreign tourists, has caused the growth of the number of visitors, which manifests joint interests such as the protection and preservation of the environment and that in turn there is adequate economic growth at the local level.

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